

YouthMappers: A Hybrid Movement Design for the OpenStreetMap Community of Communities

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Increasingly ubiquitous open spatial technologies offer the opportunity for new actors to participate in creating knowledge about the places where they live and work, and where they connect to others around the world. The situated nature of data production processes affects mappers and mapping, is generally understudied despite its potential to make meaningful contributions to purposeful continuously improved design of such processes for an open community like OpenStreetMap (OSM). University students are one set of actors who have grown significantly in their visibility and contributions to OSM, in part through the establishment of YouthMappers in 2015. This inclusive international network of university-based, youth-led, faculty-mentored chapters currently on more than 320 campuses in 67+ countries [1] works to mobilize and support university student mapping action that responds to humanitarian and development needs by creating and using an ecosystem of data and tools centered on OSM. The YouthMappers experience lends itself to explore interesting questions about the cultural and organizational aspects of data production and usage practices in OSM, in order to improve them. In this case, we explore these aspects as they occur within and through the academic sector, particularly through the hands and eyes of student youth. As a consortium design, this networked set of local groups works on the one hand, to create and use data on their local campuses and home communities, and on the other, to remotely contribute data on imagery-visible features in response to humanitarian, development, and knowledge needs wherever they may occur around the globe. Furthermore, they act not only within the OSM “community of communities” framework [2], but also within an existing global infrastructure of academic institutions with its own set of shared educational aims, knowledge generating practices, and cultural norms. Meanwhile, students are motivated both by learning and using new skills and workforce competencies as well as by the opportunity to participate in the world’s largest volunteered geographic information project and the activities that make common good use of the data. So how do YouthMappers navigate these different aims within these different spaces of action?

To address this question, two aspects of this experience are the focus of attention in this study. First, this study aims to identify what are some of the qualitative and quantitative characteristics distinguishing the performance of YouthMappers as an academic-based

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community within OSM. Second, this study aims to better understand how the design approach taken by and on behalf of YouthMappers reinforces an identity as unique contributors. The design of the YouthMappers consortium within the context of OSM is both purposeful and justified by the literature [3,4]. Our approach builds upon our typology of understanding the internal OSM community dynamic as a multi-scaled, social ecosystem, which can be categorized across non-mutually exclusive groups using typical descriptors such as sector-based characteristics; modality of engagement with OSM (i.e. editors; map-based services providers; data consumers); and around social bonds formed for purposes (e.g. HOT) or identity (e.g. GeoChicas), or place (e.g. local OSM communities), as well as other dimensions of connectedness. The case of YouthMappers demonstrates a multi-scaled social ecosystem that could be tagged as public/non-profit, academic, editor-consumer, purpose-driven, identity and place-based [4].

Study results should be contextualized with an understanding of the current state of higher education, particularly the present tension around higher ed institutions' purpose as sites for both workforce preparation and global citizenship [5]. YouthMappers members sector, role, purpose, and identity are integral to the design of the rewards and motivations for participation. Trends in higher education, especially this tension, have been integral to the design and engagement characteristics of YouthMappers. For example, both formal credit-bearing or credential-enhancing experiences and resources are combined with the fieldwork and social group leadership model of youth-led chapters. The latter point on youth leadership is situated with reference to scholarship on the global targets of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as the currently predominant discourse for international action across humanitarian domains and within the academic sector alike. This review sets up three interlocking hypotheses we anticipate can be rejected: H1: (Action-of-Performance) Participating youth either map only locally or remotely, but not both; H2: (Hybrid-Roles) Participating youth cannot simultaneously pursue personal aims to prepare themselves for the workforce and to express their identities as global citizens; and H3: (Movement-Minded) Participating youth cannot articulate the impacts/benefits of actions undertaken for broader communities or society through their work with OSM, nor identify the roles/contributions of youth action in this work for the common good. Data to test the first hypothesis relate to performance and include a range of metrics of participation [6–8], statistics of known users [9], and a review of data from other studies of YouthMappers' editing contributions [10]. To track and monitor the mapping activity and growth of YouthMappers, we analyzed the OSM database to identify contributions from usernames provided to the network as being associated with a particular YouthMappers chapter in annual reports and queries [11]. This contributor-centric approach is not comprehensive, but considered to more closely represent the active community than a hashtag-based approach, as the database contains a sufficiently large estimated sample of the YouthMappers population to provide pattern analysis on the quantity and types of contributions they make to OSM, where response rates are estimated at 78% [11]. Local mapping is defined as any edit made within the same country as the location of the chapter for which each username is identified; remote mapping is defined as edits in any other country than where their home chapter is based. Edits were tabulated by building, road, amenity, and all features. Gender is known for approximately 41% of usernames and a descriptive analysis of performance shows different patterns of editing. YouthMappers whose edits are exclusively local represent 29% of the community; whose edits are exclusively remote only 23% of the community; and nearly half

(48%) map both local and remote. Output by tendency to edit however is greatly skewed towards the half who map both locally and remotely, a subgroup which accounts for fully 96% of the edits, compared to only 1% and 3% respectively for exclusively local and exclusively remote mappers. When removing outliers (defined as the 8 super mappers who produce more than three times the standard deviation from the median), this pattern persists, whereby YouthMappers who map both locally and remotely produce 91% of edits, compared to only 3% and 6% of exclusively local and exclusively remote mappers. By edit type, 60.4% of buildings are mapped locally, 56.6% of highways and 94.9% of amenities are mapped by YouthMappers from the same country as where the feature appears. Gender-based comparisons reveal that women mappers tend to be slightly more likely to map remotely, least likely to map highways locally and map amenities at the same rates.

Data to test the second hypotheses relate to identity and come from the long-running student-authored blogs [12], as well as a global survey of YouthMappers collected in 2019 accompanied by a qualitative set of member queries to iterate interpretation of the survey results [11,13]. YouthMappers blogs are student-authored and available for all members as an opportunity to vocalize insights about mapping experiences and perspectives. Two years of blog narratives were reviewed [12] and used as reflective or open-ended writing that education literature validates for textual analysis to explore both authentic task and qualitative assessment via informal writing that is coded by independent multiple readers who are neither authors nor program managers using both a deductive and an inductive (emergent) content analysis framework [12]. These blogs were also categorized by the region of the author and by gender and included only blogs from students who spoke to experiences, excluding announcements or events. All 302 utterances were coded and analyzed based upon the locus of affect, that is being from an individual or a group or collective perspective. Results demonstrated that regardless of region, students tended to discuss positive aspects of learning as members of a group as well as learning as individuals, where positive affect occurred one-third to one-fourth more frequently in the former category. These utterances point to ease in navigating the tension of individual benefits of participation (e.g. preparing oneself for work) while at the same time enjoying group benefits (e.g. being part of a collective of citizen action). Between 20 to 30% of respondents reported receiving a paid internship as a direct result of YouthMappers participation, and for more than 10% of them, doing so led to a job offer [11].

Data to test the third hypothesis come from the same sources and a set of case studies on the SDGs [13]. In particular, our surveys reveal across all regions, across gender, across various lengths of participation time, that students reflect above 90 % that they value YouthMappers participation because of motivation for being a good citizen, social responsibility, living a well-rounded life, as well as for finding a well-paying job and finding a rewarding career [11]. Some differences are perceived by region of origin. YouthMappers from the Global North tended to agree more strongly with knowing how to explain benefits of science to society, while YouthMappers from the Global South were statistically significantly more likely to know how mapping could impact their local community [11].

These results reveal a spectrum of interests balancing local and global mapping across the consortium, and across regions, and other axes of participation. They also indicate the extent to which youth reflect on local benefits, including personal skill development, versus global citizenship, including how they understand the meanings of their actions for SDGs, locally and globally. Detected differences by gender, world region, and

duration of participation are interpreted and validated with additional qualitative data. The results confirm that we may reject all three hypotheses, validating the model. Findings build a case for understanding the potential of community design to advance the goals of OSM broadly. We also point to the role of university systems as third space sites for enabling performance and identities for youth action [5,14]. This means universities can serve as hybrid organizations that, when linked to global discourses on issues like sustainability (SDGs) and open data (OSM), can mobilize youth to create and participate in “hybrid movements” [5] that are both frameworks of performance and spaces of identity to advance OSM communities. Our findings offer insights for how other types of communities could leverage their existing milieu in ways that strengthens OSM broadly. The details and configuration need to be designed according to the framework of what type of community and what context and institutional milieu they are situated within [2,4]. Ultimately, the idea of hybrid movements encourages OSM to embrace a pluralistic, inclusive and diverse set of communities that not only bring individual contributions but leverages other systems like the landscape of academia was systematically enlisted via the YouthMappers design.

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